

2-ADIC PROPERTIES OF GENERALIZED FIBONACCI NUMBERS

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Abstract

Let T_n denote the generalized Fibonacci number of order k defined by the recurrence $T_n = T_{n-1} + T_{n-2} + \cdots + T_{n-k}$ for $n \geq k$, with initial conditions $T_0 = 0$ and $T_i = 1$ for $1 \leq i < k$. In this paper we use the theory of 2-adic analytic functions to study T_n and the shifted sequence $T_n + 1$, focusing on properties of its 2-adic valuation.

1. Introduction

Let T_n denote the generalized Fibonacci number of order k defined by the recurrence $T_n = T_{n-1} + T_{n-2} + \cdots + T_{n-k}$ for $n \geq k$, with initial conditions $T_0 = 0$ and $T_i = 1$ for $1 \leq i < k$. The determination of the 2-adic valuation $\nu_2(T_n)$ has been pursued by several authors [4, 5, 9, 11] in recent years, resulting in the following determinations:

Theorem 1 ([3]). *For order $k = 2$, the 2-adic valuation of the n -th Fibonacci number $T_n = F_n$ is given by*

$$\nu_2(F_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 3 \pmod{6}, \\ \nu_2(n) + 2, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{6}. \end{cases}$$

Theorem 2 (Marques and Lengyel [5], 2014). *For order $k = 3$, the 2-adic valuation of the n -th Tribonacci number T_n is given by*

$$\nu_2(T_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \not\equiv 0, 3 \pmod{4}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 3 \pmod{8}, \\ \nu_2(n) - 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \\ \nu_2(n+4) - 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 4 \pmod{8}, \\ \nu_2((n+1)(n+17)) - 3, & \text{if } n \equiv 7 \pmod{8}. \end{cases}$$

Theorem 3 (Sobolewski [9], 2017). *For even order $k \geq 4$, the 2-adic valuation of the n -th generalized Fibonacci number T_n is given by*

$$\nu_2(T_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{k+1}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv k+1 \pmod{2k+2}, \\ \nu_2(n) + \nu_2(k-2) + 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2k+2}. \end{cases}$$

Theorem 4 ([11], 2018). *For odd order $k \geq 5$, the 2-adic valuation of the n -th generalized Fibonacci number T_n is given by*

$$\nu_2(T_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \not\equiv 0, k \pmod{k+1}, \\ \nu_2(k-1), & \text{if } n \equiv k \pmod{2k+2}, \\ \nu_2(k-3), & \text{if } n \equiv -1 \pmod{2k+2}, \\ \nu_2(n) - \nu_2(k+1) + 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2k+2}, \\ 2 + \nu_2(m-z), & \text{if } n = (2k+2)m + k + 1, \end{cases}$$

where z is some 2-adic integer satisfying $z \equiv \frac{k-1}{4-2k} \pmod{2^{3\nu_2(k-1)-1}\mathbb{Z}_2}$.

Regardless of the parity of k , the description of the valuation of T_n depends essentially on the congruence class of n modulo $2k+2$, and is usually constant on such congruence classes. When k is even, there is only one such congruence class on which $\nu_2(T_n)$ is non-constant, while for odd $k \geq 5$ there are two such classes. In the case of odd $k \geq 5$, the formula for $\nu_2(T_n)$ is not completely explicit as the value of z is not known exactly, although for any such k it can be computed to reasonable 2-adic precision. Indeed, it was the conjecture of Lengyel and Marques [4] that $12z + 6 = -43266$ in the case $k = 5$ that inspired us [11] to prove Theorem 4. Eventually, our numerical computations revealed that -43266 is not the correct value, although the actual value is a 2-adic integer which agrees with -43266 to twenty 2-adic digits. Ruiz and Luca [7] then gave a proof that $12z + 6$ is not an integer for $k = 5$, but otherwise the nature of these values of z appears to be unknown, whether rational, algebraic, or transcendental. From the Binet formula of the recurrence and the analysis of [11], we know that each such value of z is the unique 2-adic zero of an algebraic linear combination of 2-adic exponential functions to algebraic bases, and the values do not appear to be integers based on numerical computations. It seems reasonable to conjecture for all odd $k \geq 5$, the values of z are transcendental 2-adic integers.

When k is odd, it is also apparent that $\nu_2(T_n)$ takes every possible nonnegative integer value, distinguishing this case from the even orders k , for which $\nu_2(T_n)$ never takes the value 2. In general $\nu_2(T_n)$ takes all nonnegative integer values ν except for $2 \leq \nu \leq \nu_2(2k-4)$ when $k \geq 4$ is even. As a consequence, we observe that the sequence (T_n) cannot be dense in the ring \mathbb{Z}_2 of 2-adic integers when k is even. However, we will show (Theorem 7 below) that for even k the sequence (T_n) is in fact dense in the group of units of \mathbb{Z}_2 . This is not true for odd k .

In this article, we consider also the shifted sequence $P_n = T_n + 1$ and determine, as explicitly as possible, its 2-adic valuation. We find that, as with (T_n) , the behavior of the valuation is dependent on the congruence class of n modulo $2k + 2$; the behavior differs depending on the parity of k ; and in particular, when k is odd, the behavior depends on a single 2-adic integer z whose exact value and algebraic nature are unknown. The result is as follows:

Theorem 5. *If $k \geq 2$, then for all integers n we have*

$$\nu_2(P_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{k+1}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv i \pmod{k+1}, \quad 2 \leq i \leq k-1 \\ \nu_2(k), & \text{if } n \equiv k \pmod{2k+2}, \\ \nu_2(k-4), & \text{if } n \equiv -1 \pmod{2k+2}, \quad (k \neq 4) \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{2k+2}. \end{cases}$$

When $k = 4$ and $n = 10m - 1$, we have $\nu_2(P_n) = 3 + \nu_2(m) + \nu_2(m + 1)$. In the remaining case where $n = (2k + 2)m - k$, we have

$$\nu_2(P_n) = \begin{cases} 2 + \nu_2(m), & \text{if } k \text{ is even,} \\ 3 + \nu_2(m) + \nu_2(m - z), & \text{if } k \text{ is odd,} \end{cases}$$

where $z \in \mathbb{Z}_2$ is some 2-adic integer satisfying $z \equiv \frac{k-3}{2k-4} \pmod{2^3\mathbb{Z}_2}$.

Remark. We observe from this theorem that when k is even, the valuation $\nu_2(P_n)$ always takes on every nonnegative integer value, a property which does not hold when k is odd; in particular, when k is odd the valuation $\nu_2(P_n)$ never takes the value 2. This is a reversal of the situation for $\nu_2(T_n)$.

While the sequences (T_n) are not 2-adically continuous functions of n except when the order k is of the form $k = 2^e - 1$, any lacunary subsequence $(T_{(2k+2)n+j})$ with gaps of length $2k + 2$ is given by a 2-adic analytic function on a large 2-adic disc, that is, a power series which converges rapidly for n in the ring \mathbb{Z}_2 of 2-adic integers. This principle, developed in [11], allows us to determine much of the general behavior of (T_n) from relatively few values.

2. 2-adic Analytic Functions

We summarize the analytical results from [11] concerning the sequences (T_n) which we need. This first set of congruences was proved by induction from the recurrence $T_{n+1} = 2T_n - T_{n-k}$, which is implied by the defining recurrence for (T_n) .

Proposition 1. *For all integers r we have*

$$T_{r(k+1)+i} \equiv 1 \pmod{2^i}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq k-1,$$

$$T_{r(k+1)+k} \equiv \begin{cases} k-1, & r \text{ even,} \\ 3-k, & r \text{ odd,} \end{cases} \pmod{2^k},$$

$$T_{r(k+1)} \equiv \begin{cases} 4r-2rk, & r \text{ even,} \\ 2rk-4r+2, & r \text{ odd.} \end{cases} \pmod{2^{k+1}}.$$

The main tool of [11] was the existence of 2-adic analytic functions which interpolate the sequence (T_n) in congruence classes modulo $2k+2$. We let \mathbb{Z}_2 denote the ring of 2-adic integers, \mathbb{Q}_2 the field of 2-adic numbers, and \mathbb{C}_2 the completion of an algebraic closure of \mathbb{Q}_2 . The 2-adic valuation $\nu_2(n)$ of an integer n is equal to the highest power of 2 which divides n , with the convention that $\nu_2(0) = +\infty$. This valuation extends uniquely to \mathbb{C}_2 , on which it takes rational values.

Theorem 6. *For each $j \in \mathbb{Z}$ there exists a function $g_j(x) = \sum_{m \geq 0} a_m x^m$ which is analytic on a large disc in \mathbb{C}_2 , containing \mathbb{Z}_2 , such that $g_j(n) = T_{2(k+1)n+j}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. The coefficients a_m are 2-adic integers which satisfy*

$$\nu_2(a_m) \geq \begin{cases} m + S_2(m) - 1, & k \text{ odd,} \\ m + S_2(m), & k \text{ even,} \end{cases}$$

where $S_2(m)$ denotes the sum of the binary digits of m .

One may approximate the coefficients a_m of such an analytic function by computing $g_j(n)$ for several integers n and solving a system of linear equations. As a simple case which is suitable for our purposes here, for any exponent r , considering

$$g_j(2^r) - g_j(-2^r) = 2^{r+1}a_1 + 2^{3r+1}a_3 + 2^{5r+1}a_5 + \dots \tag{2.1}$$

leads to the determination

$$a_1 \equiv \frac{g_j(2^r) - g_j(-2^r)}{2^{r+1}} \pmod{2^{2r+4}\mathbb{Z}_2}, \tag{2.2}$$

and similarly

$$a_2 \equiv \frac{g_j(2^r) + g_j(-2^r) - 2g_j(0)}{2^{2r+1}} \pmod{2^{2r+4}\mathbb{Z}_2}. \tag{2.3}$$

Taking $j = 1$, for example, by computing $g_1(1) = T_{2k+3} = 2^{k+2}(2k-3) - 12k + 21$ and $g_1(-1) = T_{-2k-1} = 13 - 4k$, we get an estimate

$$a_1 \equiv \frac{(-12k + 21) - (13 - 4k)}{2} = -4k + 4 \pmod{2^4\mathbb{Z}_2} \tag{2.4}$$

for the linear coefficient of $g_1(x)$ (except when $k = 2$, where this congruence holds only modulo 2^3).

The other important tool for our analysis is the theory of Newton polygons. For a polynomial or power series $f(x) = \sum_{i \geq 0} a_i x^i \in \mathbb{C}_2[x]$, the *Newton polygon* of f is the upper convex hull of the set of points $\{(i, \nu_2(a_i)) : i \geq 0\}$. A basic property ([2], Ch. IV.3, Lemma 4; [6], Theorem 9.1) is that the Newton polygon of f has a side of slope m and horizontal run l if and only if f has l zeros (counted with multiplicity) $\alpha_i \in \mathbb{C}_2$ with $\nu_2(\alpha_i) = -m$.

3. 2-adic Behavior of (T_n) for Even k

In [11] we brought the theory of 2-adic analytic functions to bear on the determination of $\nu_2(T_n)$, focusing primarily on the case of odd order k . In this section we make some observations concerning the case of even k . We begin with an alternate proof of Sobolewski’s Theorem 3 using 2-adic analytic functions.

Alternate proof of Theorem 3. All cases except for $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2k+2}$ follow directly from Proposition 1. For the remaining case, we give a proof featuring the analytic function $g_0(x) = \sum_m a_m x^m$ which interpolates $(T_{(2k+2)n})$. Put $a = \nu_2(k-2)$. It is clear that $a_0 = T_0 = 0$, and from Proposition 1

$$g_0(n) = T_{(2k+2)n} \equiv (8 - 4k)n \pmod{2^{k+1}} \tag{3.1}$$

for all integers n . Taking $r = a - 1$ in (2.2) then shows that $\nu_2(a_1) = \nu_2(8 - 4k) = a + 2$. It follows from (3.1) that $\nu_2(g_0(n)) = \nu_2(a_1 n)$ as long as $\nu_2(a_1 n) \leq k$, that is, $\nu_2(n) \leq k - a - 2$. Therefore we suppose that $\nu_2(n) \geq k - a - 1$; under this assumption it easily follows that for $i \geq 2$

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_2(a_i n^i) &\geq 3 + 2\nu_2(n) \geq 3 + \nu_2(n) + (k - a - 1) \\ &= \nu_2(n) + a + 2 + (k - 2a) > \nu_2(n) + a + 2 = \nu_2(a_1 n), \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

so that $\nu_2(a_i n^i) > \nu_2(a_1 n)$ for all $i > 1$. Therefore in all cases we have $\nu_2(g_0(n)) = \nu_2(a_1 n) = \nu_2(n) + a + 2$, proving the theorem. \square

Since $\nu_2(T_n)$ never takes the value 2 when k is even, it follows that the sequence (T_n) cannot be dense in the ring \mathbb{Z}_2 of 2-adic integers. However, the sequence is dense in the unit group of this ring.

Theorem 7. *Let T_n denote the generalized Fibonacci number of even order k . Then the sequence (T_n) is dense in the unit group \mathbb{Z}_2^\times of the ring of 2-adic integers. Consequently, for every odd integer N and every positive integer s there exists $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $T_n \equiv N \pmod{2^s}$.*

Proof. Our proof will be based on the following principle of the analytic functions $g_j(x) = \sum_m a_m x^m$ which interpolate (T_n) in residue classes modulo $2k + 2$: if $\nu_2(a_1) = 2$, then the image $g_j(\mathbb{Z}_2)$ equals the coset $a_0 + 4\mathbb{Z}_2$. To see this, we note that $\nu_2(a_i) > 2$ for all $i > 1$. Therefore if $y \in a_0 + 4\mathbb{Z}_2$, the Newton polygon of $g_j(x) - y$ has vertices $(0, \nu_2(a_0 - y))$ and $(1, 2)$ which determine its unique side of nonpositive integer slope, corresponding to its unique root of nonnegative valuation; all other sides have positive slope. By Hensel's Lemma [2, Theorem 3], this root lies in \mathbb{Z}_2 ; therefore there exists $x \in \mathbb{Z}_2$ such that $g_j(x) = y$.

The theorem then follows by observing that for $j = 1$, the analytic function $g_1(x)$ has $a_0 = 1$ and $a_1 \equiv 4 - 4k \pmod{2^3\mathbb{Z}_2}$ as in (2.4), while for $j = -k$ a similar calculation shows that the analytic function $g_k(x)$ has $a_0 = -1$ and $a_1 \equiv 12 - 4k \pmod{2^3\mathbb{Z}_2}$. Therefore the image of (T_n) is dense in both $1 + 4\mathbb{Z}_2$ and $-1 + 4\mathbb{Z}_2$, so it is dense in \mathbb{Z}_2^\times . \square

4. 2-adic Valuation of $T_n + 1$

In our proof of Theorem 5 we will use $g_j(x)$ to denote the analytic function which interpolates $P_{(2k+2)x+j}$, a notation which differs from Theorem 6 only by changing the value of the constant coefficient a_0 by one.

Proof of Theorem 5. All cases of the theorem except for $n \equiv 1 \pmod{k + 1}$ and the one exceptional case where $k = 4$ follow immediately from Proposition 1.

For the case $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2k + 2}$, we consider the analytic function $g_1(x) = \sum_{m \geq 0} a_m x^m$ which interpolates $P_{(2k+2)x+1}$. We have the estimate $a_1 \equiv 4 - 4k \pmod{2^4}$ from (2.4) for the linear coefficient of $g_1(x)$. Since the constant coefficient $a_0 = 2$, and $\nu_2(a_i) > 1$ for $i > 0$, we have $\nu_2(g_1(x)) = 1$ for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}$, giving the result for $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2k + 2}$.

For the case $k = 4$ and $n = 10m - 1$, we calculate that $P_{-1} = 0$, $P_{-11} = 0$, $P_{-21} = 16$, and $P_9 = 80$. Consider the analytic functions $g_j(x) = \sum_i a_i x^i$ which satisfy $g_j(m) = P_{10m+j}$ for $m \in \mathbb{Z}$, whose coefficients a_i satisfy $\nu_2(a_i) \geq i + S_2(i)$ for all $i > 0$. First take $m = 2x$, $j = -1$ and consider the function $f(x)$ given by

$$P_{20x-1} = f(x) = g_{-1}(2x) = 2a_1x + 4a_2x^2 + \dots$$

which satisfies $f(0) = 0$ and $f(-1) = 16$. Since all terms of the series except the first term $2a_1$ have valuation at least 5, we must have $\nu_2(a_1) = 3$ and $\nu_2(f(x)) = 3 + \nu_2(2x)$ for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}$, proving the stated result when m is even. Next take $m = 2x - 1$ and consider the function

$$P_{20x-11} = h(x) = g_{-1}(2x - 1) = g_{-11}(2x) = 2a_1x + 4a_2x^2 + \dots$$

which satisfies $h(0) = 0$ and $h(1) = 80$. Since all terms of the series except the first term $2a_1$ have valuation at least 5, we must have $\nu_2(a_1) = 3$ and $\nu_2(h(x)) =$

$3 + \nu_2(2x)$ for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}$, proving the stated result when m is odd. Therefore in any case we have $\nu_2(P_{10m-1}) = 3 + \nu_2(m) + \nu_2(m + 1)$.

Suppose k is even and $n = (2k+2)m - k$. The analytic function $g_{-k}(x) = \sum_i a_i x^i$ satisfies $g_{-k}(0) = 0$, $g_{-k}(1) = 4k - 4$, and $g_{-k}(-1) = 12k - 28$. We see from (2.2) that $a_0 = 0$ and $a_1 \equiv -4k + 12 \pmod{2^3\mathbb{Z}_2}$, so that $\nu_2(a_1) = 2$ when k is even. Therefore $\nu_2(g_{-k}(m)) = \nu_2(a_1 m) = 2 + \nu_2(m)$ for $m \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Finally, suppose k is odd and $n = (2k+2)m - k$. The analytic function $g_{-k}(x) = \sum_i a_i x^i$ satisfies $g_{-k}(0) = 0$, $g_{-k}(1) = 4k - 4$, $g_{-k}(-1) = 12k - 28$, $g_{-k}(-2) = 40k - 88$, and $g_{-k}(2) \equiv 24k - 40 \pmod{2^{k+2}}$. We see from (2.2), (2.3) that $a_0 = 0$, $a_1 \equiv -4k + 12 \pmod{2^6}$, $a_2 \equiv 8k - 16 \pmod{2^6}$, and $a_3 \equiv a_4 \equiv 0 \pmod{2^6}$. Thus $\nu_2(a_1) \geq 3$, the first two vertices of the Newton polygon are $(1, \nu_2(a_1))$ and $(2, 3)$, and all other sides have slope at least 1. Therefore $g_{-k}(x)$ has a zero at $x = 0$ and exactly one other zero $x = z$ which satisfies $\nu_2(z) = \nu_2(a_1) - 3$ and

$$0 = g(z) \equiv a_1 z + a_2 z^2 \pmod{2^6 z^3 \mathbb{Z}_2},$$

which implies $z \equiv \frac{k-3}{2k-4} \pmod{2^3\mathbb{Z}_2}$.

Now write $g_{-k}(x) = \sum_m a_m x^m = x(x - z) \sum_m b_m x^m$. Then $b_0 = -a_1/z$ has $\nu_2(b_0) = 3$, and $b_m = -(a_1 + a_2 z + \dots + a_{m+1} z^m)/z^{m+1}$ for $m \geq 1$. Since $g_{-k}(z) = 0$ we have $\nu_2(b_1) \geq 6$ and $\nu_2(b_m) \geq m + 2$ for all $m > 0$. Therefore $\sum_m b_m x^m$ also converges on $D = \{x \in \mathbb{C}_2 : \nu_2(x) > -1\}$. Since $\nu_2(b_m) > 3$ for all $m > 0$, we have $\nu_2(\sum_m b_m x^m) = 3$ for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}_2$. It follows that $\nu_2(g_{-k}(x)) = \nu_2(x) + \nu_2(x - z) + 3$ for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}_2$, completing the proof. \square

As with the case of even order k , the generalized Fibonacci sequences (T_n) of odd order k are 2-adically dense in two of the four congruence classes modulo 4.

Theorem 8. *Let T_n denote the generalized Fibonacci number of odd order k . Then the sequence (T_n) is dense in $4\mathbb{Z}_2$ but not in $2\mathbb{Z}_2$. The sequence (T_n) is also dense in $1 + 4\mathbb{Z}_2$ but not in $1 + 2\mathbb{Z}_2$. Consequently, for every integer $N \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4}$ and every positive integer s there exists $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $T_n \equiv N \pmod{2^s}$.*

Proof. Consider the analytic function $g_0(x) = \sum_{m \geq 0} a_m x^m$ which interpolates $T_{(2k+2)m}$. Since $g_0(0) = 0$, $g_0(1) = 2^{k+1}(2k - 3) - 4k + 8$, and $g_0(-1) = 4k - 8$, we determine from (2.2), (2.3) that $\nu_2(a_1) = 2$ and $\nu_2(a_i) > 2$ for $i > 1$. Therefore, as in the proof of Theorem 7, for every $y \in 4\mathbb{Z}_2$ there exists $x \in \mathbb{Z}_2$ such that $g_0(x) = y$. Thus (T_n) is dense in $4\mathbb{Z}_2$. However, from Proposition 1 we observe that the values of (T_n) which are even but not multiples of 4 all lie in a single congruence class modulo 2^k , and therefore cannot be dense in $2 + 4\mathbb{Z}_2$. Thus (T_n) is not dense in $2\mathbb{Z}_2$.

A similar calculation using the analytic function $g_{1-k}(x) = \sum_{m \geq 0} a_m x^m$ which interpolates $T_{(2k+2)x+1-k}$ shows that $a_0 = 1$, $a_1 \equiv 8k - 20 \pmod{2^4\mathbb{Z}_2}$, $\nu_2(a_1) = 2$, and $\nu_2(a_i) > 2$ for $i > 1$, so that (T_n) is dense in $1 + 4\mathbb{Z}_2$. However, since $\nu_2(P_n)$ never takes the value 2, (T_n) cannot be dense in $1 + 2\mathbb{Z}_2$. \square

5. Small Values of k

We conclude with some illustrations of these theorems for specific small values of k , including some numerical computations of the z values.

Corollary 1. *If $k = 2$, then for all integers n we have*

$$\nu_2(P_n) = \nu_2(F_n + 1) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 2, \pm 1 \pmod{6}, \\ 2 + \nu_2(m), & \text{if } n = 6m - 2. \end{cases}$$

Corollary 2. *If $k = 3$, then for all integers n we have*

$$\nu_2(P_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0, 3 \pmod{4}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 1, \pm 2 \pmod{8}, \\ 3 + \nu_2(m) + \nu_2(m - z), & \text{if } n = 8m - 3, \end{cases}$$

where z is some 2-adic integer satisfying $z \equiv -601592 \pmod{2^{20}\mathbb{Z}_2}$.

Proof. To estimate z , we used the lacunary recurrence

$$T_{n+16} = 131T_{n+8} - 3T_n + T_{n-8} \tag{5.1}$$

[10, eq. (3.6)] to calculate (T_n) for negative integers in the congruence class $n \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$, determining that for $m = -601592$, $n = 8m - 3 = -4812739$ we have $\nu_2(P_n) = 26$, showing that $\nu_2(-601592 - z) = 20$ by comparison with the formula from Theorem 5. □

Remark. A referee has observed that a previously published paper [1] contains an incorrect formula for $\nu_2(T_n + 1)$ in the case $k = 3$. Lemma 2 of [1] stated that the valuation is given by

$$\begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0, 3 \pmod{4}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 1, \pm 2 \pmod{8}, \\ 3 + \nu_2(m) + \nu_2(m - 8), & \text{if } n = 8m - 3 \text{ and } m \neq 8, \\ 15, & \text{if } n = 8m - 3 \text{ and } m = 8. \end{cases} \tag{5.2}$$

This formula is incorrect because it would imply that (T_n) is not continuous as a 2-adic function of n on \mathbb{Z}_2 , having a discontinuity at $n = 61$, which contradicts [11, Theorem 3]. The above formula (5.2) involves $\nu_2(m - 8)$ where the correct formula from Corollary 2 has $\nu_2(m - z)$ where $z \equiv -601592 \pmod{2^{20}\mathbb{Z}_2}$; since $\nu_2(8 - z) = 9$, the above formula (5.2) will give an incorrect valuation whenever $n > 61$ satisfies $n \equiv 61 \pmod{2^{12}}$. The smallest counterexample to (5.2) occurs when $n = 4157$, for which $\nu_2(T_{4157} + 1) = 18$ and the above formula predicts the valuation to be 15.

We also observe that the above corollary implies that the Tribonacci sequence (T_n) has the property that $\nu_2(T_n+1)$ never takes the values 2,4,6,8, or 9, although it takes all other nonnegative integer values. If $n = 8m - 3$ and $\nu_2(m) \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ then $\nu_2(m - z) = \nu_2(m)$ and thus $\nu_2(P_n) \in \{3, 5, 7\}$. If $\nu_2(m) > 3$ then $\nu_2(m - z) = 3$, while if $\nu_2(m) = 3$ then $\nu_2(m - z) > 3$, so in either of these cases $\nu_2(P_n) \geq 10$.

Corollary 3. *If $k = 4$, then for all integers n we have*

$$\nu_2(P_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 1, \pm 2, \pm 3 \pmod{10}, \\ 2, & \text{if } n \equiv 4 \pmod{10}, \\ 2 + \nu_2(m), & \text{if } n = 10m - 4, \\ 3 + \nu_2(m) + \nu_2(m + 1), & \text{if } n = 10m - 1. \end{cases}$$

Corollary 4. *If $k = 5$, then for all integers n we have*

$$\nu_2(P_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0, 5 \pmod{6}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \pm 4 \pmod{12}, \\ 3 + \nu_2(m) + \nu_2(m - z), & \text{if } n = 12m - 5, \end{cases}$$

where z is some 2-adic integer satisfying $z \equiv -953013 \pmod{2^{20}\mathbb{Z}_2}$.

Proof. To estimate z , we used multisection as in [10] to determine that the lacunary recurrences (T_{12n+j}) all have characteristic polynomial

$$p(x) = x^5 - 3333x^4 - 758x^3 - 10x^2 + 5x - 1. \tag{5.3}$$

We then used this lacunary recurrence to calculate (T_n) for negative values of n congruent to $-5 \pmod{12}$, determining that for $m = -953013$, $n = 12m - 5 = -11436161$, we have $\nu_2(P_n) = 23$, showing that $\nu_2(-953013 - z) = 20$ by comparison with the formula from Theorem 5. \square

Remark. This corollary shows that for $k = 5$, $\nu_2(P_n)$ takes on every nonnegative integer value except 2 and 3.

Corollary 5. *If $k = 6$, then for all integers n we have*

$$\nu_2(P_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{7}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 6, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \pm 4, \pm 5 \pmod{14}, \\ 2 + \nu_2(m), & \text{if } n = 14m - 6. \end{cases}$$

Corollary 6. *If $k = 7$, then for all integers n we have*

$$\nu_2(T_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \not\equiv 0, 7 \pmod{8}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 7 \pmod{16}, \\ 2, & \text{if } n \equiv -1 \pmod{16}, \\ \nu_2(n) - 2, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{16}, \\ 2 + \nu_2(m - z), & \text{if } n = 16m + 8, \end{cases}$$

where z is some 2-adic integer satisfying $z \equiv -11687 \pmod{2^{22}\mathbb{Z}_2}$.

Corollary 7. *If $k = 7$, then for all integers n we have*

$$\nu_2(P_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0, 7 \pmod{8}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \pm 4, \pm 5, \pm 6 \\ & \pmod{16}, \\ 3 + \nu_2(m) + \nu_2(m - z), & \text{if } n = 16m - 7, \end{cases}$$

where z is some 2-adic integer satisfying $z \equiv -558438 \pmod{2^{21}\mathbb{Z}_2}$.

Remark. This corollary shows that for $k = 7$, $\nu_2(P_n)$ takes on every nonnegative integer value except 2, 4 and 5.

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